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Research Article

**AWARENESS AND PRACTICE OF EVIDENCE BASED
MEDICINE AMONG PHYSICIANS IN TAIF, SAUDI ARABIA**Reem Alghamdi¹, Rawan Halabi², Elham Alrubai³

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Abstract:

Background: Evidence-based medicine (EBM) is a new term that is important for improving clinical skills and practice medicine. Local and international studies showed that there is high awareness of evidence-based medicine but lack in practice due to variable barriers. Thus, this study aims to determine the awareness, practice and barriers of Evidence Based Medicine (EBM) among physicians in Taif city, Saudi Arabia.

Methods: This is a cross sectional study using a modified questionnaire that was distributed to 200 physicians from 2017-2018. This study took place in Taif university and hospitals in Taif city.

Results: It showed that participants tend to agree in application of EBM and practicing EBM it improves the quality of patient care. The frequency of practicing and using the EBM, were 64% from participants were practiced the EBM in their days. Also, the current study showed that 52.8% participants have no time to practice EBM during their day.

Conclusion: The physicians showed acceptable level of knowledge and attitude on EBM. There is lack of practice due to inadequacy of time and unavailability of access to internet in their working place.

Keywords: Evidence based medicine; Physician; Saudi Arabia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Evidence-based medicine (EBM) is a new term that is important for improving clinical skills and practice medicine. The term “evidence-based medicine” is relatively new. In fact, as far as we can tell, investigators from McMaster’s University began using the term during the 1990s. EBM was defined as “a systemic approach to analyze published research as the basis of clinical decision making.” Then in 1996, the term was more formally defined by Sacket et al., who stated that EBM was “the conscientious and judicious use of current best evidence from clinical care research in the management of individual patients.” (Jeffrey et al.,2005).

In an international in Belgium, the Netherlands, the United States, the United Kingdom and Australia. The findings indicate that most managers they studied have positive attitudes towards EBP. However, lack of time and a limited understanding of scientific research are perceived as major barriers towards EBM. (Villanueva et al.,2017). In Mexico City the majority of them did not know the characteristics that define the EBM and phases of the process for its practice. (Aguirre Raya et al.,2016).

In Kuwait the EBM awareness was low to the EBM. In Bahrain, family physicians are using EBM in their daily work, especially noted among those physicians who took EBM courses. In Dubai, UAE showed negative attitude to EBM in the Dubai PHC sector. Due to lack of encouragement to attend EBM courses and senior physicians resist adoption of EBM. In Jordan, the study showed positive attitude toward EBM, however it described different personal, interpersonal and organizational barriers that affect the implementation of the EBM. (Al-Barrak et al.,2014).

In Saudi Arabia a study in Riyadh showed a low level of awareness but lack of practice. (Al-Ansary and Khoja, 2002). In Dammam showed an overall

positive attitude to EBM. And in Abha city showed acceptable level of knowledge but also lack of practice. (Al-Musa, 2010), there is lack of studies that assess the attitude of all physicians in all specialties in Taif city, Saudi Arabia and worldwide. Thus, this study aims to determine the awareness, practice and barriers of Evidence Based Medicine (EBM) among General physicians, Residents, specialist and consultants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This is a cross sectional study using a modified questionnaire that was distributed to 200 physicians working in the university and hospitals and classified into general physicians, residents, specialist and consultants. 187 out of 200 completed the questionnaire (Response rate 93.5%). The data collected during period from October 2017 to January 2018. That was done using interviewing the questionnaire with the targeted staff in the university and hospitals. Additionally, online questionnaire was shared through the social media applications such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Telegram and Facebook.

The questionnaire was modified copy from (McColl. Et al, 1998). It was 4 sections and 26 items written in English, including demographic data (age, gender and specialty). Data analysis by statistical package for social science program (SPSS).

RESULTS:

Participants characteristics were showed in table 1 as 57.3% from participants were females while 42.7% were males. Most of them ranged in age between 20 to 29 years with 80.3%, as well as 84.8% had been licensed less than 5 years. Lastly, position of participants was categorized into 4 groups, with highest percentage for resident position (50%), then 42.7% for GPs and only 6.2%, and 1.1% for specialists and consultants, respectively.

Table1: participants characteristics (n=178)

Parameters		Freq.	%
gender:	Female	102	57.3%
	Male	76	42.7%
age group :	20 - 29 years	143	80.3%
	30 - 39 years	31	17.4%
	40 - 49 years	2	1.1%
	50+ years	2	1.1%
For how many years have you been licensed?	0 - 5 years	151	84.8%
	5 - 10 years	20	11.2%
	11 - 15 years	3	1.7%
	+ 15 years	4	2.2%
Your position:	General physician	76	42.7%
	Resident	89	50.0%
	Specialist	11	6.2%
Consultant		2	1.1%

In table 2, it illustrated the frequency of practicing and using the EBM, were 64% from participants were practiced the EBM in their days. Regards frequency of practicing, they been distributed as highest percentage for 1 to 4 times a week (37.7%), then daily bases (35.1%), and lowest percentage for practicing 1 to 4 times per month with 27.2%.

Table2: Participants frequency for using EBM

Parameters		Freq.	%
Do you practice evidence based medicine in your day (n = 178)	Yes	114	64.0%
	No	64	36.0%
How many time/s do you practice EBM (n = 114)	Daily	40	35.1%
	1-4 times a week	43	37.7%
	1-4 times a month	31	27.2%

According to scoring system in table 3, perception of participants regards practicing the EBM was scored in table 4.

Table3: scoring system

Class	Indicator
1 – 1.66	Agree
1.67 – 2.33	Neutral
2.34 – 3.00	Disagree

It showed that participants tend to agree in their answers in related to their aware of the EBM, application of EBM as necessary in the practice of medical field, practicing EBM in improves the quality of patient care, Literature and research findings are useful in their day-to-day practice, EBM helps them make decisions about patient care, and patients satisfaction rate will increase if they incorporate EBM into practice.

In another way, participants tent to be neutral in their perception in regards to that EBM is lacking to

support most of the interventions that they use with their patients, and they tent as well to be neutral that learning EBM is a part from academic preparation, specially that they stated that they not sure about receiving formal training in search strategies for finding research relevant to their practice. Lastly, participants agreed that in need to increase the use of evidence in their daily practice, and they are interested in learning or improving the skills necessary to incorporate EBM into their practice.

Table4: Participants perception towards practicing the EBM (n = 178)

Parameters	Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Mean	SD	Status
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			
I am aware of the evidence based medicine.	120	67.4%	49	27.5%	9	5.1%	1.38	.581	Agree
Application of Evidence Based Medicine is necessary in the practice of medical field.	155	87.1%	22	12.4%	1	0.6%	1.13	.359	Agree
Practicing evidence- based medicine improves the quality of patient care.	149	83.7%	26	14.6%	3	1.7%	1.18	.427	Agree
Literature and research findings are useful in my day-to-day practice.	111	62.4%	59	33.1%	8	4.5%	1.42	.579	Agree
EBM helps me make decisions about patient care.	134	75.3%	39	21.9%	5	2.8%	1.28	.507	Agree
Patients satisfaction rate will increase if I incorporate EBM into my practice	120	67.4%	49	27.5%	9	5.1%	1.38	.581	Agree
evidence based medicine is lacking to support most of the interventions I use with my patients *	40	22.5%	112	62.9%	26	14.6%	1.92	.606	Neutral

I learned the foundations for EBM as part of my academic preparation.	89	50.0%	54	30.3%	35	19.7%	1.70	.780	Neutral
I have received formal training in search strategies for finding research relevant to my practice.	59	33.1%	66	37.1%	53	29.8%	1.97	.795	Neutral
I need to increase the use of evidence in my daily practice.	152	85.4%	21	11.8%	5	2.8%	1.17	.448	Agree
I am interested in learning or improving the skills necessary to incorporate EBM into my practice.	143	80.3%	24	13.5%	11	6.2%	1.26	.563	Agree

*Reverse question

In table 5, participants showed their awareness level towards EBM, where 58.4% from them have not access to current research through professional journals in their paper form, with only 41.6% who have an access. Results in current study showed that 52.8% from participants have not time to access databases during their day, and

only 40.4% from total participants agreed with facility supports the use of current research in practice. Participants were divided equally either have the ability to access relevant databases and the Internet at facility or not through answering equally with yes and no (41.6% for both). Lastly, they tend to be agree in the ability to access relevant databases and the Internet at home or locations other than their facility, with 65.2%.

Table5: Participants awareness towards the EBM (n = 178)

Parameters	Yes		No		Do not know	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
I have access to current research through professional journals in their paper form.	74	41.6%	104	58.4%	0	0.0%
I have time to access databases during my day.	84	47.2%	94	52.8%	0	0.0%
My facility supports the use of current research in practice.	72	40.4%	48	27.0%	58	32.6%
I have the ability to access relevant databases and the Internet at my facility.	74	41.6%	74	41.6%	30	16.9%
I have the ability to access relevant databases and the Internet at home or locations other than my facility.	116	65.2%	44	24.7%	18	10.1%

To measure the frequency that participants Read/review research/literature related to their clinical practice, results observed that about 42.7% read one article per week

,while about 41.6% read about 2 to 5 articles per week. In another way, the frequency results for use professional literature and research findings in the process of clinical decision making showed that less than one time been 41%, and 2 to 5 times been 39.3%. finally, frequency results for times of use MEDLINE \ Up-to-date or other databases to search for practice-relevant literature/research showed that highest percentage for 2 to 5 times use (32%), then 6 to 10 times use (27%).

Table6: Frequencies of reading/review research/literature, and time frequencies for depending on EBM (n = 178)

Parameters	0 – 1		2 – 5		6 - 10		11 - 15		+ 16	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Read/review research/literature related to my clinical practice (articles)	76	42.7%	74	41.6%	19	10.7%	1	0.6%	8	4.5%
Use professional literature and research findings in the process of clinical decision making (times)	73	41.0%	70	39.3%	20	11.2%	3	1.7%	12	6.7%
Use MEDLINE \ Up-to-date or other databases to search for practice-relevant literature/research (times).	36	20.2%	57	32.0%	48	27.0%	9	5.1%	28	15.7%

To find out the relationship between gender and practice of EBM, results showed that no -statistically significant relationship between gender and times for practice of EBM (table 7).

Table 7: relationship between Gender and if they practice EBM and frequency for practice (n = 178)

Parameter			Gender		Total	df	P-value
			Female	Male			
Do you practice evidence based medicine in your day.	Yes	Freq.	68	46	114	1	.398
		%	59.6%	40.4%	100.0%		
	No	Freq.	34	30	64		
		%	53.1%	46.9%	100.0%		
How many time/s do Daily you practice EBM	Daily	Freq.	24	16	40	2	.977
		%	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a week	Freq.	26	17	43		
		%	60.5%	39.5%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a month	Freq.	18	13	31		
		%	58.1%	41.9%	100.0%		

To find out the relationship between age and practice of EBM, results showed that no difference between age groups in practicing EBM (P-value more than 0.05), as well as no statistically significant relationship between age groups and times for practice of EBM (table 8).

Table 8: relationship between Age groups and if they practice EBM and frequency for practice (n = 178)
Age Groups

			20 - 29	30 - 39	40 - 49	50+	Total	df	P-value
Do you practice evidence based medicine in your day.	Yes	Freq.	93	17	2	2	114	3	.328
		%	81.6%	14.9%	1.8%	1.8%	100.0%		
	No	Freq.	50	14	0	0	64		
		%	78.1%	21.9%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
How many time/s do you practice EBM	Daily	Freq.	30	7	2	1	40	6	.430
		%	75.0%	17.5%	5.0%	2.5%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a week	Freq.	38	5	0	0	43		
		%	88.4%	11.6%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a month	Freq.	25	5	0	1	31		
		%	80.6%	16.1%	0.0%	3.2%	100.0%		

To find out the relationship between years of practice and practice of EBM, results showed that no difference between years of practice and practicing EBM (P-value more than 0.05), as well as no statistically significant relationship between years of practice and times for practice of EBM (table 9).

Table 9: relationship between years of licensed and if they practice EBM and frequency for practice (n = 178)

**For how many years have
you been licensed?**

			0 - 5 years	5 - 10 years	11 - 15 years	+ 15 years	Total	df	P- value
Do you practice evidence based medicine in your day.	Yes	Freq.	93	16	2	3	114	3	.420
		%	81.6%	14.0%	1.8%	2.6%	100.0%		
	No	Freq.	58	4	1	1	64		
		%	90.6%	6.3%	1.6%	1.6%	100.0%		
How many time/s do you practice EBM	Daily	Freq.	29	9	0	2	40	6	.357
		%	72.5%	22.5%	0.0%	5.0%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a week	Freq.	37	4	1	1	43		
		%	86.0%	9.3%	2.3%	2.3%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a month	Freq.	27	3	1	0	31		
		%	87.1%	9.7%	3.2%	0.0%	100.0%		

Lastly, in table 10 showed the relationship between position and practice of EBM, where results showed that difference between position and practicing EBM was exist (P-value less than 0.05). according to results it observed that who practice BM in GPs

group less than who do not practice it, while percentage of users of EBM from residents, specialist and consultants been higher than who do not use it. However, no statistically significant relationship between position and times for practice of EBM was seen.

Table 10: relationship between position and if they practice EBM and frequency for practice (n = 178)

			Your position				Totaldf	P-value	
			GP	Res.	Spec.	Cons.			
Do you practice evidence based medicine in your day.	Yes	Freq.	37	65	10	2	1143	.001	
		%	32.5%	57.0%	8.8%	1.8%	100.0%		
	No	Freq.	39	24	1	0	64		
		%	60.9%	37.5%	1.6%	0.0%	100.0%		
How many time/s do you practice EBM	Daily	Freq.	11	22	5	2	40	6	.278
		%	27.5%	55.0%	12.5%	5.0%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a week	Freq.	18	22	3	0	43		
		%	41.9%	51.2%	7.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
	1-4 times a month	Freq.	8	21	2	0	31		
		%	25.8%	67.7%	6.5%	0.0%	100.0%		

DISCUSSION:

The current study showed that the physicians have high awareness to evidence based medicine (EBM), which come in accordance to the findings of a studies locally in Riyadh, Dammam and abha. And internationally in Belgium, Netherlands, United States, United Kingdom and Australia. In addition to the high awareness the participants showed that they tend to agree that application of EBM is necessary in the practice of medical field, and practicing EBM it improves the quality of patient care.

In general more than half of the participants (64%) practice evidence based medicine in their days. Regards frequency of practicing, they been distributed as highest percentage for 1 to 4 times a week (37.7%), then daily bases (35.1%), and lowest percentage for practicing 1 to 4 times per month with 27.2%.

according to results it observed that who practice BM in GPs group less than who do not practice it, while percentage of users of EBM from residents, specialist and consultants been higher than who do not use it.

Lastly, participants agreed that in need to increase the use of evidence in their daily practice, and they are interested in learning or improving the skills necessary to incorporate EBM into their practice.

Obstacle: An obstacle of this study was the usage of a self-reported questionnaire to collect data about awareness and practice of EBM, which was prone to recall bias.

Recommendation: is to study the barriers of practicing and how it affect the patients' health.

CONCLUSION:

The physicians showed acceptable level of knowledge and attitude on EBM.

there was a gap between their knowledge and practice. this gap could be attributed to what was addressed by the physicians, namely, inadequacy of time and unavailability of access to internet in their working place. the better knowledge of the trained than the untrained physicians could draw the attention towards the importance of training courses relevant to EBM

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